

Supplementary Materials: Empirical Scoring Results

AI Transparency: Governance Compliance or Stakeholder Requirements? An Empirical Analysis of Australian Government AI Transparency Statements

Note: This document presents the full empirical scoring results for 92 Australian Government agencies evaluated against the 20-criterion evaluation instrument developed under Version 1.1 of the DTA Policy for Responsible Use of AI in Government (effective 1 September 2024). Scores were assigned on a 0–2 ordinal scale: 0 = not addressed, 1 = partially addressed, 2 = fully addressed. A further 8 agencies within scope had no published transparency statement at the time of data collection (May 2025) and are listed separately. Section 5 presents qualitative evaluator observations and criterion-level notes for agencies where these were recorded. All scoring sheets and the evaluation instrument are available in the full replication package.

1. Summary Statistics

Agencies in scope	100	Mean total score	28.9 / 40
Statements evaluated	92	Median total score	31.0 / 40
No statement published	8	Score range	0 – 40
Scoring scale	0–2 per criterion	Max possible score	40

2. Per-Criterion Score Summary

Table 1 presents the distribution of scores across all 20 evaluation criteria. Criteria are colour-coded by thematic group: blue = AI Use & Planning, orange = Governance & Risk Management, grey = Public Accountability & Accessibility.

#	Criterion	Group	n	Score 0 (%)	Score 1 (%)	Score 2 (%)	Mean score
1A	Current AI use intent	AI Use	91	7%	18%	76%	1.69
1B	Future AI adoption intent	AI Use	91	13%	52%	35%	1.22
2A	Usage pattern classification	AI Use	84	12%	12%	76%	1.64
2B	Domain identification	AI Use	84	13%	12%	75%	1.62
3A	Direct public interaction	AI Use	84	27%	12%	61%	1.33
3B	Human review prior to impact	AI Use	83	18%	19%	63%	1.45
4A	Performance monitoring	Gov.	84	12%	50%	38%	1.26
4B	Formal oversight mechanisms	Gov.	84	12%	26%	62%	1.50
5	Legal/regulatory compliance	Gov.	83	6%	28%	66%	1.60
6	Negative impact mitigation	Gov.	83	12%	40%	48%	1.36
7A	DTA policy alignment	Gov.	83	6%	6%	88%	1.82
7B	Australian AI ethics alignment	Gov.	83	19%	28%	53%	1.34
8	Public accessibility	Pub.	92	2%	11%	87%	1.85
9A	Publication date	Pub.	91	32%	7%	62%	1.30
9B	Last updated date	Pub.	91	31%	9%	60%	1.30
10	Review/update cycle	Pub.	91	7%	11%	82%	1.76
11	Plain language clarity	Pub.	91	1%	3%	96%	1.95
12	Public contact mechanism	Pub.	91	10%	21%	69%	1.59
13A	Homepage discoverability	Pub.	92	12%	37%	51%	1.39
13B	Navigation ease	Pub.	92	11%	37%	52%	1.41

4. Full Agency Scoring Table

Table 2 presents complete criterion-level scores for all 92 evaluated agencies, sorted by total score (descending). Cell shading indicates score value: teal = 2 (fully addressed), orange = 1 (partial), red = 0 (not addressed). Column headers are colour-coded by thematic group.

Agency	1A	1B	2A	2B	3A	3B	4A	4B	5	6	7A	7B	8	9A	9B	10	11	12	13A	13B	Tot.	
Australian Electoral Commission (AEC)	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	40
Department of Industry, Science and Resourc...	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	39
Australian Public Service Commission (APSC)	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	38
Australian Transaction Reports and Analysis...	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	38
Digital Transformation Agency (DTA)	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	38
Fair Work Commission (FWC)	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	38
Department of Climate Change, Energy, Envir...	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	37
Department of Finance (Finance)	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	37
IP Australia (IP Australia)	2	2	2	2	0	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	37
National Health and Medical Research Council...	2	1	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	37
Australian Securities and Investments Commi...	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	36
Department of Veterans' Affairs (DVA)	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	36
Geoscience Australia (GA)	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	36
Parliamentary Budget Office (PBO)	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	36
Professional Services Review (PSR)	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	36
Services Australia (Services Australia)	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	36
Office of the Commonwealth Ombudsman (Ombud...	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	35
Royal Australian Mint	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	35
Screen Australia (SA)	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	35
Australian Radiation Protection and Nuclear...	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1	34
Australian Skills Quality Authority (ASQA)	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	34
Department of Education	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	34
Department of Employment and Workplace Rela...	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	34
National Health Funding Body (NHFB)	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	34
Office of the Auditing and Assurance Standa...	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	34
Office of the Australian Accounting Standar...	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	34
Office of the Fair Work Ombudsman (FWO)	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	34
Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS)	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	33
Australian Competition and Consumer Commiss...	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	33
Australian Financial Security Authority (AF...	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	33
Australian Research Council	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	33

Agency	1A	1B	2A	2B	3A	3B	4A	4B	5	6	7A	7B	8	9A	9B	10	11	12	13 A	13 B	Tot.	
Department of the House of Representatives ...	2	2	2	1	0	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	33
National Library of Australia (NLA)	2	1	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	0	2	2	2	1	2	2	33
National Offshore Petroleum Safety and Envi...	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	33
Parliamentary Workplace Support Service (PW...	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	33
Productivity Commission (PC)	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	33
Workplace Gender Equality Agency (WGEA)	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	33
Attorney-General's Department (AGD)	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	32
Office of the Official Secretary to the Gov...	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	32
Australian Fisheries Management Authority (...)	2	2	2	2	0	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	31
Australian Institute of Family Studies (AIFS)	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	0	2	2	1	1	1	31
Australian Law Reform Commission (ALRC)	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	0	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	31
Australian Office of Financial Management (...)	1	2	2	2	0	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	0	2	2	2	31
Australian Taxation Office (ATO)	2	1	2	2	0	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	1	2	2	2	2	2	31
Clean Energy Regulator (CER)	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	1	2	2	0	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	31
Department of Health and Aged Care (Health)	2	0	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	31
Department of Parliamentary Services (DPS)	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	0	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	31
Safe Work Australia (SWA)	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	0	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	31
TEQSA	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	31
Australian National Audit Office (ANAO)	2	2	1	1	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	2	2	1	1	1	30
National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA)	0	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	30
National Indigenous Australians Agency (NIAA)	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	0	2	2	1	2	2	2	30
Office of the Inspector-General of Aged Car...	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	0	1	2	2	2	2	2	30
Sport Integrity Australia (SIA)	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	0	2	2	0	2	2	1	2	2	2	30
Administrative Review Tribunal (ART)	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	0	1	2	2	2	0	0	0	29
Aged Care Quality and Safety Commission (AC...	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	0	1	1	1	29
Office of Parliamentary Counsel (OPC)	2	1	2	2	0	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	29
Old Parliament House (OPH)	2	1	2	2	0	2	1	0	1	2	2	1	2	0	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	29
Department of the Prime Minister and Cabine...	1	0	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	28
Australian Institute of Criminology (AIC)	2	0	2	2	2	0	0	1	2	0	2	1	2	2	0	1	2	2	2	2	2	27
Australian Prudential Regulation Authority ...	2	0	2	2	0	0	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	27
Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Fo...	2	1	2	2	0	0	2	2	1	0	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	27
Department of the Treasury (Treasury)	2	1	2	2	2	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	27
Inspector-General of Intelligence and Secur...	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	—	—	—	—	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	27

Agency	1A	1B	2A	2B	3A	3B	4A	4B	5	6	7A	7B	8	9A	9B	10	11	12	13A	13B	Tot.
Australian Communications and Media Authori...	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	0	1	2	2	0	1	26
Australian Trade and Investment Commission ...	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	0	0	1	2	2	0	0	26
Commonwealth Director of Public Prosecution...	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	2	0	2	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	26
Commonwealth Grants Commission (CGC)	1	1	0	0	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	0	0	2	2	2	1	2	26
Department of Home Affairs (Home Affairs)	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	26
Climate Change Authority (CCA)	2	1	0	0	0	2	0	1	2	1	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	25
Organ and Tissue Authority (OTA)	0	1	0	0	2	0	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	25
Asbestos and Silica Safety and Eradication ...	1	2	1	1	0	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	24
Australian Transport Safety Bureau (ATSB)	1	0	0	0	2	0	1	1	2	2	2	0	2	2	0	2	2	0	2	2	23
Department of Infrastructure, Transport, Re...	1	1	2	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	23
Independent Parliamentary Expenses Authorit...	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	23
NDIS Quality and Safeguards Commission (NDI...	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	23
Office of the Australian Information Commis...	0	1	0	0	2	0	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	0	1	2	2	1	1	23
Office of the Special Investigator (OSI)	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	0	0	2	2	1	2	2	23
Australian Centre for International Agricul...	2	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	2	2	2	2	1	0	0	0	2	0	1	1	20
National Anti-Corruption Commission (NACC)	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	20
Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (DF...	1	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	1	2	0	2	2	2	1	1	0	1	1	19
Domestic, Family and Sexual Violence Commis...	2	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	19
Cancer Australia (CA)	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	2	2	0	2	2	2	0	0	18
National Capital Authority (NCA)	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	18
National Archives of Australia (NAA)	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2	2	0	2	2	1	2	2	17
Seafarers Safety, Rehabilitation and Compen...	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	1	0	2	0	2	0	2	0	2	2	1	1	17
Department of Social Services (DSS)	2	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	16
Future Fund Management Agency (FFMA)	1	1	1	0	2	—	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	16
Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	15
National Blood Authority (NBA)	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	15
Inspector-General of Taxation (IGT)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0	—	—	—	—	—	0	0	0
National Reconstruction Fund Corporation (N...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2. Full criterion-level scores per agency. Sorted by total score (descending). Max score = 40.

5. Qualitative Evaluator Observations and Notes

This section presents the qualitative observations and criterion-level evaluator notes recorded during scoring. Observations provide an overall characterisation of each statement. Notes record specific criterion-level reasoning, including justification for borderline scores and notable disclosure practices. Notes are presented as recorded by evaluators and lightly edited for readability. Agencies without recorded observations or notes are not listed. Agencies are sorted alphabetically.

Agency	Overall Observation	Criterion-level Notes
Administrative Review Tribunal (ART)	No AI use currently; future planning focus, governance described.	1A: The Tribunal provides ReadSpeaker and Google Translate services for users of our website. 1B: The Tribunal clearly defines its current use, future use, and the cases where it will NOT use AI systems 2A: intends to use AI in the domains of service delivery, corporate and enabling services, policy and legal or compliance and fraud detection; 2B: Intended future use of AI will cover the following key domains. 3A, : ReadSpeaker and Google Translate services for Tribunal website users do not require Tribunal staff to operate 3B: Where the Tribunal does use, or, intends to use AI in the domains of service delivery, corporate and enabling services, policy and legal or compliance and fraud detection; it shall be subject to human oversight. 5: Compliance with applicable legislation and regulations, mentions of AI ethics principles, DTA and other regulations 12: Tribunal's usage of AI, please contact AI@art.gov.au. 9A does not show first published, 10: Reviewd annully mentioned, 11 fully understandable language, 13: hard to find, buried, needs search
Aged Care Quality and Safety Commission (ACQSC)	Strong AI application in regulatory support, fairness highlighted.	1B: NO future plans for using AI, 3A: The department isn't using AI applications where the public can directly interact with or be impacted by AI. 4A: general mention under Safe and responsible AI adoption, 6: our policies meet the proposed mandatory guardrails for AI in high-risk settings, &B:: General mention of repsonible AI use, 9A no mention of first published, 10B: no explicit frequency of update mentioned, 13: indirect, buried takes a few clicks to figure out
Asbestos and Silica Safety and Eradication Agency (ASSEA)	Minimal AI use; ethical governance planning.	1B: potential future use-cases mentioned, 3A: ASSEA does not propose to use AI where the public may directly interact with or be significantly impacted by it. , 3B: No mention of the human review, 4: Dedicated monitoring and oversight section given, 5: Use of AI by the Agency will be in accordance with all relevant legislation, associated regulations, and Government frameworks. , 9B: fno last update date mentioned, 10: This statement will be reviewed annually, and updated if there are changes to the use of AI within the agency. 11: understandable, 12: public contact email provided For questions about this statement or for further information on the Agency's usage of AI, please contact enquiries@asbestossafety.gov.au
Attorney-General's Department (AGD)	Full AI use; excellent transparency, governance, and risk detail.	1B: No future plans , 6: Nodiscussion on public harm and risk assessment, 9: no last published or updated date mentioned
Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS)	Strategic use of AI to enhance productivity and analytics.	1B: no fiture AI use mentioned, 31: The public has no direct interaction with any of our systems that utilise AI technologies and will not be impacted by our use of AI. 3B: No mention of human oversight to AI outputs, 4B: general mention of oversight, 5: no mention of specific bodies, 9B: no last updated date, 12: public contact form provided rather than email,
Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research (ACIAR)	Very cautious exploration phase; future ethical framework outlined.	1A: Clearly mentions how they are using MS Copilot, 1B: No future mention of the AI use, 3B: any AI-produced content must be reviewed before publication. 4B: No mention of oversight body 9: No publish or update date available, 10: does not commit to review , 11: clear understandable

Agency	Overall Observation	Criterion-level Notes
Australian Communications and Media Authority (ACMA)	Limited administrative use of AI; future governance commitment.	3A: Currently, ACMA does not plan to use AI in services that the public may directly interact with or be significantly impacted by 3B: but all systems are tested by humans to ensure they behave as expected before they are released. 4B: specific mention of AI governing body he ACMA has developed an overarching agency approach to AI and has established an AI Steering Committee to assess the opportunities and risks in using AI within ACMA. 6: Mentions risk in monitoring and governing AI section, but no mitigation strategies discussed. 9B: No mention of last updated 10: This statement will be reviewed annually, or when any significant change is made to our approach to AI. 11: no technical jargon 13A: no exclusive page for AI transparency statement - section under planning and priorities
Australian Competition and Consumer Commission (ACCC)	Administrative AI tools, no use in consumer decisions.	1A: AI use clearly mentioned: The ACCC's use of AI is aimed at improving workplace productivity for staff. This includes: 2B: The domains used for AI applications focuses on the following areas, 3A: We do not currently deploy AI as part of the ACCC's direct interaction with the public, 6: mentions risk with no mitigation, 9A: first published is clearly mentioned, 9B: last updated is not mentioned, 10: commits to regular reviews, 11: understandable 12: takes to the contact us page with call and form enquiry
Australian Electoral Commission (AEC)	Good AI support for administrative processes with human oversight highlighted.	1B: The second trial will be conducted to evaluate the use of Microsoft 365 Copilot Pro on corporate tasks within the AEC 3B: Nor does the AEC's use of AI have any other significant impact on the public and AI is not used as part of any AEC interaction with the public. 12: Enquires may be directed to media@aec.gov.au 13: takes some effort to find the link landing on website
Australian Financial Security Authority (AFSA)	Limited AI use in internal administration; good governance commitment.	1A: Current usage is specified 2A, 2B: AFSA is using AI in the domain of Corporate and Enabling, and usage patterns of Analytics for Insights 3A: This does not include the use of AI where the public may directly interact with, or be significantly impacted by, AI 3B: without a human intermediary or intervention.6: General mention of risks 9A: No mention of published date, 10: This statement will be reviewed annually, when there is a significant change to AFSA's approach to AI, or when any new factor materially impacts the existing statement's accuracy. 11: understandable language 12: For further enquiries, contact: info@afsa.gov.au 13B: intuitive to find
Australian Fisheries Management Authority (AFMA)	Limited AI use for operational risk prediction; moderate technical clarity.	1B: We are investigating the use of AI as part of our Data Transformation and Electronic Monitoring Program. 3B: We do not use AI in compliance, auditing or decision-making processes without human oversight. 6: our risks are identified and addressed 7B: our AI use is appropriately governed, our engagement with AI is confident, safe and responsible 9A: no first published date mentioned 10: For further information or enquiries about AFMA's adoption of AI, you can contact us directly at info@afma.gov.au. 11: understandable language. 12: For further information or enquiries about AFMA's adoption of AI, you can contact us directly at info@afma.gov.au.
Australian Institute of Criminology (AIC)	Limited AI use mainly for research data analytics; strong ethical practices.	1B: No future use of AI mentioned 3A: The AIC does not propose to use AI where the public may directly interact with or be significantly impacted by it. 3B: No mention of human oversight 4A no mention of evaluation 6: No mention of risks involved or risk mitigation 7B: use AI for research purposes, while maintaining ethical standards, transparency and ensuring data protection.12: please contact frontdesk@aic.gov.au. 13: easily findable

Agency	Overall Observation	Criterion-level Notes
Australian Institute of Family Studies (AIFS)	Limited AI use mainly in administrative functions.	1A: AI use clearly mentioned and categorised to domains and usage patterns 1B: future use not mentioned 2A 2B: AI across the corporate and enabling, and scientific domains in the analytics for insights and workplace productivity usage patterns. 3A: We do not propose to use AI where the public may directly interact with or be significantly impacted by it. 3B: and for all users of AI to review and validate any content generated by the services 4: monitoring and oversight mechanisms explained in detail under executive monitoring, RAI policy and training and assistance sections 6: mentions risk with no mitigation 7B: We have developed and continue to maintain an internal Responsible AI usage policy that aligns with advice and guidance provided by the DTA and other agencies for using AI services responsibly. 9A: first published given (B: last update not provided 10: no regular review mentioned 11: understandable language 12: public contact method provided please contact ai@aifs.gov.au.
Australian Law Reform Commission (ALRC)	No AI use currently; future ethical governance planned.	1A:The ALRC has not yet used AI in any formal setting or supported any Law Reform activities to date. 1B: Our intention is to trial the adoption of AI in 2025 and beyond as part of the Australian Government's commitment to digital innovation. 2: The ALRC will use AI in the domain of Corporate and Enabling, and usage pattern of Workplace Productivity. 3A: At this time, we are not using AI to support any of our Law Reform activities or engage with the public. 3B: Not rely on the authenticity or veracity of content generated by AI, without external verification. 6: general mention of risk assessment and mitigation 7A: no reference to DTA 9A: first published not mentioned 10: It will be updated as our approach to AI changes, and at least every twelve months. 11: understandable 12: you can contact us directly at info@alrc.gov.au.
Australian National Audit Office (ANAO)	Clear AI monitoring and strong human oversight frameworks.	1B: Future use specified: The ANAO is exploring how AI may be used to improve business operations by enhancing efficiency, while ensuring quality and transparency in decision-making. 2: Domains and usage patterns generally covered. 3A: The ANAO does not use AI tools that interact with the public and considers the limited use of AI within the organisation to have a low impact on the public. 3b: no mention of human overview involved 9B: last updated not provided 6 general mention of risk and risk mitigation 10 does not commit to regular review 12: Contact page provided 13: not easily findable, buried
Australian Office of Financial Management (AOFM)	Limited AI support for operational efficiency.	1B: Our intention is to leverage AI to drive innovation, improve operational efficiency, and support the broader goal of managing the government's debt portfolio. 2A: We currently use AI to assist in workplace productivity. 2B: These applications focus on streamlining processes, automating routine tasks and demonstrating best-practice approaches. 3B: AI is not used in compliance, auditing or decision-making without having a human-in-the-loop. 6: The AOFM has safeguards in place to mitigate risks and support responsible use of AI. 8: available at the homepage 9A: mentions DTA compliance 10: The AOFM's Statement will be reviewed and updated at the earliest of these junctures 11: understandable 13: findable and intuitive
Australian Prudential Regulation Authority (APRA)	Minimal AI use; planning governance for future applications.	1A: current usage is clearly specified 1B: No future use specified 2A: (DTA domains of Corporate and Enabling, and Workplace Productivity *) 2 B: APRA's use of AI is limited to the development of use cases within internal departments, focused on improving operational efficiencies. 3B: does not say if the human intermediary is involved 4B: APRA has designated a pane fir monitoring and governance 6: general mention of risk identification and mitigation 8: direct link provided 9A: publish date not provided 9B: last update date provided 10: This statement will be updated as and when APRA's approach to AI changes or when developments materially affect the statement's accuracy, and at least every twelve months. 11 understandable 12: For inquiries about APRA's AI use, please email: aiao@apra.gov.au.

Agency	Overall Observation	Criterion-level Notes
Australian Public Service Commission (APSC)	Governance planning for AI adoption; operational use not yet extensive.	1A: We are currently investigating implementing a trial of Microsoft Co-Pilot internally to investigate how it can be used to enhance workplace productivity, through streamlining internal processes and automating routine tasks. 1 B: Outcomes from this trial will be used to inform the Commission's consideration of how AI productivity tools may be used and applied within our business. 2:This trial will be undertaken within the domains of Corporate Services and the usage patterns of Workplace Productivity 3: we are currently not using AI in any way that members of the public may directly interact with, or be significantly impacted by, without a human intermediary or intervention. 4B: clearly mentions of governance board and policies 6: general mention of risk assessment with a risk assessment undertaken in consultation with IT Security. 8 easily available 9A: first published provided 9B: last updated provided 10: We will update this statement at least every twelve months or when 11: understandable 12: email provided 12: you can contact us directly at Artificial.Intelligence@apsc.gov.au. 13: linked and intuitive to find
Australian Radiation Protection and Nuclear Safety Agency (ARPANSA)	Good AI use in safety data analysis; human oversight well documented.	1B: potential use described in detail under workplace productivity heading 3A: ARPANSA's use of AI does not involve direct interaction with the public or pose any significant impact to individuals.4A: performance is not mentioned in detailed 6" mentions risk with no mitigation 9B: last updated not provided10: general mention of regular reviews 12: email provided For further inquiries about our AI use, please contact us at ai@arpansa.gov.au , 13: buried in home links and non-intuitive to find
Australian Research Council	Strong strategic use of AI in research funding.	1B: potential use clearly mentioned 4A: general mention of evaluation 4B: implied oversight mentioned without any detail 6: general mention of risk 9B: last update date not given 12: contact email and phone provided Phone: 02 6206 7226 cio@arc.gov.au 13B: required some effort to locate
Australian Securities and Investments Commission (ASIC)	Strong AI deployment across compliance and fraud prevention.	3A: ASIC does not use AI in any manner that allows direct interaction with the public or significantly impacts the public, without human oversight or involvement.6: general mention of risk assessment with no mitigation details 12: contact page provided 13A; buried 13B: non-intuitive to find
Australian Skills Quality Authority (ASQA)	Cautious exploration of AI for operational efficiency.	1A: current use is mentioned on workplace productivity including tools to improve, automate and streamline routine tasks and to support data and analytical insights. 1B: potential future use is defined via intent and how AI will be used section 2: Workplace productivity and analytics for insights with examples is clearly mentioned, under headings of usage patterns and domains 3B: This ensures that there is always a human directly involved (Human in the Loop, or HITL) to review and validate any outcome/s generated by AI systems, in order to maintain accountability and accuracy. 8: accessible 9A: no first published date 9: last update date available 10: ensures responsible use of AI through releasing at least an annual AI Transparency Statement 11: understandable 12: contact provided 13: directly linked and easy to find
Australian Taxation Office (ATO)	Large-scale AI use in backend support and service optimization.	3B: not all the outputs require human oversight, powering risk models to identify potential non-compliance or fraud for human review. And decision making for tax payers 4A: only general monitoring defined 6: risk mitigation not discussed 9B: last updated not provided 10: commits to regular review but no time mentioned We will review our AI transparency statement regularly and publish updates on our website. 12: contact page provided
Australian Trade and Investment Commission (Austrade)	Minor AI experimentation; governance commitment noted.	1A: The only approved tools in use currently include the Microsoft 365 CoPilot virtual assistant 1B: Austrade is interested in understanding the potential application and usage of other AI tools across our functions and to do this we will continue to undertake active research and testing with AI technologies. Austrade is also engaging in the Government's AI CoLab Alliance, supported by the APS Capability Reinvestment Fund. 2Austrade maintains visibility of AI use and classifies AI use according to the following usage patterns and domains: list of domains and patterns provided 3B: AI is only used under human supervision. The outputs of AI models are monitored for effectiveness.4B: The General Manager Digital and Technology, is the designated Accountable Official (AO) for all AI matters. They are responsible for Austrade's implementation of the whole-of-government Policy for the Responsible Use of AI in Government. 12: contact us page provided 11: understandable 13: hard to find / buried

Agency	Overall Observation	Criterion-level Notes
Australian Transaction Reports and Analysis Centre (AUSTRAC)	Limited AI use for staff productivity; governance discussed.	1A: current use of AI AUSTRAC uses generative AI tools to undertake research and discovery, and for workplace productivity purposes. 1B: AUSTRAC is considering the future adoption of AI for the purposes of Workplace Productivity and Analytics for Insights. 2 domains and usage patterns defined clearly under each section 3: AUSTRAC has not yet deployed any use of AI which directly interacts with the public or is involved in decision making and administrative action without human intervention 4: These usage patterns are currently in the pilot stage where they will be evaluated in alignment with the Policy for Responsible Use of AI in Government and internal AUSTRAC AI Policy.6: general mention of risk / risk mitigation 8: accessible online 10: will be reviewed annually, w 12: understandable 12: contact us page provided
Australian Transport Safety Bureau (ATSB)	Limited AI involvement in investigation data support.	1A:Presently, the ATSB does not utilise AI to deliver any of its services. Although, the ATSB did participate in the Australian Government trial of Microsoft 365 Copilot. 1B: no future use mentioned 2: No domain and usage patterns mentioned as they are not using AI, however mentioning this exclusively maybe in copilot trial or future usage patterns is important 3A: Currently, ATSB does not plan to use AI in services that the public may directly interact with or be significantly impacted by. 3B: does not explain human intermediary involvement 6: general mention of risk 7B: does not explain compliance with any other policy 8: accessbile 9A: first published provided 9B: last updated not provided 10: his statement will be reviewed annually, or when any significant change is made to our approach to AI. 11: understandable 13: linked directly on about us, intuitive to find
Cancer Australia (CA)	AI deployed for early cancer detection analytics; strong governance.	1A: current usage not clearly defined 2B: usage patterns not mentioned 3A: 3B: CA does not currently use AI in service delivery, specifically AI is not used in compliance, auditing or decision-making without having a human-in-the-loop. 4: Not mentioned 6: No risk mention, 7B: not aligned with any other policy or ethics principles 9B: last updated not mentioned 12: contact provided 13: burried , non intuitive for human to find - downloads as a separate document
Clean Energy Regulator (CER)	Full AI use in emissions monitoring; strong ethics, governance, and risk documentation.	4A: general mention of oversight 6: no statement about risk or risk mitigation 9A: first published not provided 13A: requires a few clicks 13B: somewhat intuitive
Climate Change Authority (CCA)	Limited AI use; future governance framework outlined clearly.	1A: the Authority has not adopted any specific AI applications in its operations 2: no mention of domains and usage patterns 3B: Any future decisions or outcomes generated by AI that could affect the public or environment will involve human oversight or intervention to ensure fairness and accountability. 4A: no mention of performance evaluation 6: general mention of risk our compliance as a part of existing governance, and risk management processes. 8 accessible 9A: first published not given 10: commits to annual review 11: language is understandable 12: contact page provided
Commonwealth Director of Public Prosecutions (CDPP)	No active AI systems; ethical frameworks outlined.	1A: Currently the CDPP does not use AI in any services or advice we provide publicly or currently use AI internally. 1B: no mention of future use 2: no mention of usage patterns or domains 3B: no mention as currently no AI 4A: no mention of evaluation mechanisms 6: No mention of risk or risk mitigation 8: easily accessible 10: commits to annual review 11: understandable 12: contact provided Email: inquiries@cdpp.gov.au 13: directly linked to homepage, easy to find
Commonwealth Grants Commission (CGC)	Future governance planning; minor AI use currently.	2: No mention of domains and usage patterns 3: The CGC does not use AI in ways that the public may directly interact with or be significantly impacted by without human intervention. 6: general mention of risk management We have established robust processes and proactive risk management strategies, 8: accessible 9 No date provided 10: commits to update annually This transparency statement is reviewed and updated annually or whenever significant changes occur. 11: understandable language 12: contact email provided Chief Operating Officer at services@cgc.gov.au. 13B: intuitive to find

Agency	Overall Observation	Criterion-level Notes
Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Forestry (DAFF)	—	1a 2a 2b were contained in the statement but not in a specific section. Can't find 3b explicitly or implicitly. 4a 4b were included in governance and accountability parts. No mention of 6. 7a is implicit. for 7b no ethical principle alignment. 8 - 12 are all clear.
Department of Climate Change, Energy, Environment and Water (DCCEEW)	—	13a 13b not easy to find and access
Department of Education	—	1b seems have no mention at all. 3a is clearly mentioned. 12 has contact. 13a, 13b hard to find.
Department of Employment and Workplace Relations (DEWR)	—	3a can be inferred. 12 has contact. 13a, 13b hard to find.
Department of Finance (Finance)	—	1b no mention at all. 3a can be implied from "our approach to AI" (chose to only do low-risk; low-risk has no direct interaction with public). 12 has contact.
Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (DFAT)	—	1b no mention. 3a clearly mentioned. 3b no mention. 4a 4b no mention. 5 not detailed, 6 no details, 7b no mention. 8 accessible. 9a 9b clear, 10 vague.
Department of Social Services (DSS)	—	1a 1b not using AI - not applicable for many parts.
Future Fund Management Agency (FFMA)	—	ffma is a special agency mostly not dealing with people
Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority	—	not using AI. 13a 13b Hard to find
Inspector-General of Intelligence and Security (IGIS)	—	not using AI.
Inspector-General of Taxation (IGT)	—	404 not found
NDIS Quality and Safeguards Commission (NDIS Commission)	Some minor administrative AI use; human oversight noted.	1A: Statement says the Commission "does not use AI ... externally (publicly) or internally." No current use rationale provided. 2A/B: No patterns named because no AI in use. 3A: Explicit denial: "does not use AI in services or advice we provide externally (publicly)". 3B: No mention of human review because no AI exists. 4A: No monitoring process described; only promise to update statement. 4B: No committee, role or policy named. 6: No discussion of risks or mitigations. 7B: Statement does not mention Australia's AI Ethics Principles. 6: Live at About us → Corporate reports → AI transparency statement. 9A: Page header "February 2025" acts as the publish date. 9B: Footer shows "Last updated 24 February 2025". "This statement will be reviewed annually or when significant changes occur." Provides a direct email: CIO@ndiscommission.gov.au. 13A: Listed under "Corporate reports" and appears in search dropdown—two clicks from homepage. 13B: Sits logically with other governance documents; no search needed.
National Anti-Corruption Commission (NACC)	—	not using AI
National Archives of Australia (NAA)	—	not using AI
National Blood Authority (NBA)	—	not using AI
National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA)	—	very vague about current use
National Health Funding Body (NHFB)	Clear AI adoption for analytics in hospital funding work.	3A: Explicit denial: "NHFB does not utilise public-facing AI applications that involve direct public interaction...". 4A: Statement promises policies ("AI governance and approval processes") but no method or frequency for monitoring AI performance. 9A: No publication date visible on the page. 9B: No last updated date shown. 12: Provides email and postal address for the AI Accountable Official.

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National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC)	Productive use of AI tools in research workflows; governance well described.	Criterion 12 deserves full marks because a clear contact channel is provided. ""contact the Director... through our Contact us page."
National Indigenous Australians Agency (NIAA)	Minimal current AI use, governance commitments outlined.	2A: Explicitly names "generative AI service Microsoft 365 Copilot". 3A: clearly stated "NIAA has not authorised the use of AI in any way that members of the public may directly interact with...". 5. Says it will "maintain compliance with applicable legislation" but cites none. 6. mentions risk without detail, "risks are identified and addressed" no mitigation process described. 7B: Uses "ethical use" language but does not name the AI Ethics Principles. 9A: Shows "published on 19 February 2025". 9B: No separate "last updated" date displayed. 12. Provides a 'Contact us' link rather than a direct email/phone. 13B: Logical placement with other governance docs; no search needed.
National Library of Australia (NLA)	Strong AI adoption for records digitization and access improvement.	7B: Mentions "ethical considerations" but does not name the eight AI Ethics Principles. 9B: No separate "last updated" stamp—only the publish date. 12: Provides a Contact us link (no direct email).
National Offshore Petroleum Safety and Environmental Management Authority (NOPSEMA)	Minimal AI use currently; governance framework for future expansion.	2A: Lists meeting transcription, document summarisation, virtual assistants, data analysis → clear patterns. 2B: "...focused on enhancing corporate and enabling functions.". 3A: "NOPSEMA does not currently use AI in service delivery..." – explicit denial. 6: Only states it will include "efforts to mitigate any potential negative impacts" – no detail. 7B: Uses the word "ethical" but never cites the 8 AI Ethics Principles. 8: Page is live under About > AI transparency statement. 9A: No separate "first published" stamp; only last updated. 9B: "Page last updated: 25 Feb 2025.". 10: "...will be reviewed annually, or whenever significant changes occur...". 12: Provides ai@nopsema.gov.au. 13B: Two clicks from homepage with no search required.
National Reconstruction Fund Corporation (NRFC)	No operational AI; high-level future policy commitment only.	1B: No forward plans for internal AI; the corporate plan only mentions "emerging technologies" in IT roadmap – not AI adoption. 5: No document links AI use to Privacy Act, DTA Policy, etc. 6: Only generic corporate plan risk text; nothing AI specific. 7A: DTA policy not referenced anywhere on the site. 7B: No mention of Australia's AI Ethics Principles. 8: Attempting common URLs (/ai transparency statement, /about us/artificial intelligence...) returns 404. 9A/9B: No statement => no dates. 11. Criterion applies only if a proper statement exists. 13A/13B: Nothing to navigate to.
Office of Parliamentary Counsel (OPC)	Minor support tools discussed; strong ethical standards described.	1A: Opening paragraph sets out why AI is being trialled: "predict service needs, improve user experience, support evidence based decisions and gain efficiencies." 2A: Lists decision making, analytics, workplace productivity, image processing. 2B: Names four domains (service delivery, compliance & fraud, policy & legal, corporate & enabling). 3B: Mentions "humans at the centre of decision making" but not explicit about every output. 4A: Commits to use of the Commonwealth AI Assurance Framework and annual review. 4B: Appoints an AI Accountable Official and says senior management will oversee projects. 6. References governance and privacy, but no description of how risks are mitigated. 7B: Uses general "ethical" language but does not name the eight AI Ethics Principles. 8: PDF linked on the Corporate reporting page (direct URL works). 9A: No explicit "published" stamp; PDF path (202502) implies Feb 2025 but not stated. 9B: No update date shown. 10: "...will be reviewed annually or when we make a significant change." 12: Provides enquiries@opc.gov.au and postal address.

Agency	Overall Observation	Criterion-level Notes
Office of the Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (AUASB)	Future orientation towards ethical AI adoption; no operational AI now.	1A: "...enhances and supports our work" and lists Microsoft 365 Copilot for analytics & productivity. 2A: Names Analytics for insights and Workplace productivity patterns. 2B: Specifies Research and Corporate & policy domains. 3A: "We do not propose using AI where the public may directly interact..." 3B: Same sentence plus policy requiring staff to review all outputs. 4B: Names Managing Director & Business Services Manager as Accountable Officials. 6: "Safe, ethical, responsible" but no specific mitigation steps. 7B: Uses "ethical" but does not list the eight AI Ethics Principles. 8: Live page; one click from "About AUASB" menu. 9A: "Released 27 / 03 / 2025" shown. 9B: No separate "last updated" stamp. 10: Will be reviewed at least every twelve months. 12: Direct email: . 13A: Listed in "About AUASB" menu; two clicks from homepage. 13B: Logical placement alongside other governance docs.
Office of the Australian Accounting Standards Board (AASB)	No AI used. Statement reflects monitoring of future developments; cautious but open stance.	1A: "We are adopting and using AI in a way that enhances and supports our work". 2A: Lists "Analytics for insights" and "Workplace productivity" under Usage patterns. 2B: Names "Research" and "Corporate and policy" as domains. 3A: "We do not propose using AI where the public may directly interact...". 4B: Managing Director & Business Services Manager named as Accountable Officials. 7B: Uses general "ethical" wording; does not list the eight AI Ethics Principles. 9B: No "last updated" stamp. 10: "...will be reviewed and updated ... at least every twelve months". 12: Direct email: .
Office of the Australian Information Commissioner (OAIC)	No AI use currently; strong ethical readiness discussed.	3A: Clear denial: OAIC does not currently use AI at all, therefore no public interaction. 3B: Human in the loop not discussed (no AI outputs to review). 7B: Uses phrases like "safe and responsible" but does not name the eight AI Ethics Principles. 9B: No separate Last updated stamp. 12: "Contact us" link plus phone 1300 363 992.
Office of the Commonwealth Ombudsman (Ombudsman)	No significant AI use; structured governance commitment.	1A: Uses AI for security monitoring of ICT systems and (pilot) summarising written complaints. 2A: Patterns implied: anomaly detection (security) & text summarisation (Azure AI pilot). 2B: Corporate ICT security + complaints handling support. 3A: No explicit statement, but all described AI is internal only → partial score. 4B: IT Governance Committee & Chief Operating Officer / CIO named as Accountable Officials. 7B: Uses "ethical, responsible" language but does not name the 8 AI Ethics Principles. 8: Dedicated page under About us → AI Transparency Statement (URL above). 10: "Statement will be reviewed annually or when AI use changes." 12: Direct email ai@ombudsman.gov.au provided. 13A/B: AI Transparency Statement is a first level item in the About us menu. Two clicks from homepage; logical placement with other governance docs.
Office of the Fair Work Ombudsman (FWO)	Good operational use of AI for workplace enforcement support.	7B: Talks about "ethical, responsible" use but does not name the 8 AI Ethics Principles. 9A: Only "Last updated 28 Feb 2025"; initial publish date not shown. 12: Provides Feedback form link but no direct email/phone. (Partial).
Office of the Inspector-General of Aged Care (IGAC)	No current AI use; ethical future adoption framework described.	1A: Describes voicemail transcription AI "to support workplace productivity and improve operational efficiency." 2A: Mentions workplace productivity (a DTA pattern). Not explicitly labelled, so partial. 2B: Use case sits in the corporate/enabling domain (internal productivity). Implicit rather than explicit → partial. 3A: Explicit denial: "does not currently use AI in any way that members of the public will be affected by, or directly interact with, without human interaction." 3B: Staff validate all AI transcripts; AI never used for decision making. 4B: Executive Committee oversees AI; Inspector General named as Accountable Official. 5: References compliance "with applicable legislation" but doesn't name any Act. 6: Bullet promises to "identify & protect the public against negative impacts" no detail. 7B: Uses "safe, ethical, responsible" wording but does not list the eight AI Ethics Principles. 8: Separate web page + PDF in Resources list. 9A/B: Page shows Publication date: 28 February 2025. No separate "last updated" stamp. 12: Provides contact@igac.gov.au and postal address. 13A/B: Listed under Resources; two clicks from homepage. Logical placement; no search needed.

Agency	Overall Observation	Criterion-level Notes
Office of the Official Secretary to the Governor-General (OOSGG)	Limited AI use; governance framework emphasized.	1A: Lists aims: “meet staff expectations... support experimentation... unlock new value” and cites limited assistive AI already in use. 3A: Says Office will “ensure it is obvious if [the public] are interacting with an AI system” implies none today but not explicit → partial. Requires business areas to “monitor and assess the value and effectiveness” and uses logging & reporting. 4A: Requires business areas to “monitor and assess the value and effectiveness” and uses logging & reporting. 4B: CIO appointed accountable official (8 Oct 2024) & must maintain an AI register. 8: Page under “Transparency & accountability” plus direct PDF link. 9A/B: Statement shows only “last updated 10 Feb 2025”; initial publish date absent. “Last updated 10 February 2025” present. 10: “Reviewed biennially or when significant changes occur.” 12: Provides a Contact page link but no direct email/phone (partial). 13A/B: “AI Transparency Statement” appears in Transparency navigation – two clicks from homepage. Logical grouping with other accountability docs.
Office of the Special Investigator (OSI)	No active AI; governance frameworks and future risk planning mentioned.	2A: No usage pattern categories (e.g. analytics, productivity) are specified. 2B: Statement never names an operational domain. 3A: Absence of any public-facing AI plus promise that data is handled securely ⇒ implicit no direct interaction (partial score). 3B: No mention of human review of AI outputs. 4B: “We have appointed an Accountable Official ... Oversight by governance bodies within the OSI.” 6: Mentions data privacy & security but no broader risk mitigation steps. 7B: No reference to the eight Australian AI Ethics Principles—only “ethics” in passing. 8: Live URL accessible via footer link “Artificial intelligence transparency statement”. 9A/B: Page shows no “Published” date. No “Last updated” field. 10: “This statement will be reviewed annually or when we make a significant change.” 12: Provides Contact us page link and mailing address (no direct email). 13A/B: Footer link + About us → Transparency path (two clicks). Logical placement; no search needed.
Old Parliament House (OPH)	Limited AI use; governance structures for future outlined.	1A: “MoAD uses AI... for contact & data matching, subtitles, data analytics, cyber security ... to create business efficiencies and reduce human error.” 2A: Explicitly mentions generative AI; cyber security ⇒ anomaly detection; analytics ⇒ insights. 2B: tates use is in the “Corporate and Enabling” domain. 3B: “Content is always thoroughly proofed and edited by MoAD staff before publication.” 4B: No named accountable official or committee. 5: Refers to “data governance & compliance requirements” but no legislation cited. 7B: No reference to the eight AI Ethics Principles. 8: Live page under About → Reports, policies and plans → AI Transparency Statement. 9A: No “Published” date shown. 9B: “Last updated 28 February 2025”. 10: “Reviewed annually or when significant change occurs.”. 12: Provides a contact form and generic email info@moadoph.gov.au (footer). 13A/B: Two clicks from homepage (About → Reports, policies & plans). Logical placement with other governance docs; no search needed.
Organ and Tissue Authority (OTA)	Exploring AI options; no current systems in use yet.	3A: Explicit denial: “OTA does not use AI in any services we provide” (i.e., no direct public interaction). 4B: Chief Operating Officer named as Accountable Official. 5: Only generic “compliance with applicable legislation”. 6: Generic bullet “identify and protect the public against negative impacts” no detail. 7B: Uses “ethical” wording, but does not list the eight AI Ethics Principles. 8: Live at donatelife.gov.au/ai/transparency statement and from About us → Corporate transparency. 9A/B: “First published February 2025”. No separate update stamp; initial publication only. “Reviewed annually or when significant change occurs”. “Contact us” link (no direct AI email) → partial. 13A/B: Two clicks via main About us → Corporate transparency (global nav). Logical placement among governance docs; no search needed.
Parliamentary Budget Office (PBO)	Strong AI use in policy and budgeting analysis.	3A: “Current use of AI at the PBO does not directly impact our clients or the Australian public.”. 3B: Statement stresses staff ownership of advice and controls, but does not say every AI output is reviewed by a human. Partial credit. 5: References “relevant legislation and regulations” but does not name any Acts. 12: “contact us” link provides enquiry form/phone, but no dedicated AI email. Partial.

Agency	Overall Observation	Criterion-level Notes
Parliamentary Workplace Support Service (PWSS)	Limited AI use, strong future governance planning.	1A: "PWSS uses AI to support analytics for insights and workplace productivity." 2A: Usage patterns explicitly listed: analytics for insights, workplace productivity. 2B: Future domains named: compliance & fraud, policy & legal, corporate & enabling. 3A: "PWSS does not use AI in any public-facing services and does not use AI to make decisions." 4B: Deputy CEO appointed Accountable Official; inter-agency AI Working Group. 5: Mentions "maintaining legal & regulatory compliance" but cites no specific Act. 7B: Uses "ethical" language; doesn't list the eight AI Ethics Principles. 8: PDF linked from About us → Publications → Artificial Intelligence Transparency. 9A/B: No "First published" stamp. "Last updated 26 February 2025" shown. 10: "Statement will be reviewed annually or when significant changes occur." Provides PWSSCorporate@pwss.gov.au, phone 1800 747 977. 13A/B: Two clicks from homepage; dedicated nav item "Artificial Intelligence Transparency". Logical placement under Publications; no search required.
Productivity Commission (PC)	AI used for analytics and policy research; human oversight emphasized.	3A: "We do not propose using AI where the public may directly interact ...". 4A: Users must review outputs, but no schedule/metrics for system performance. 5: Mentions privacy, data governance, cyber security but doesn't cite specific Acts. 6: No explicit mitigation steps beyond "safe, ethical, responsible" commitment. Uses the word "ethical" but does not list the 8 AI Ethics Principles. 9B: No "Last updated" field. 12: Email ai@pc.gov.au provided.
Professional Services Review (PSR)	Strong AI support for operational workflows; human oversight emphasized.	1B: Lists planned areas: automating enabling processes, managing/viewing medical records (clear future context). 3A: Doesn't state "public" explicitly; but says no AI in statutory decision-making and only internal comms ⇒ indirect evidence of no public interaction (partial credit). 4A: EMT monitors adoption but no review cadence or metrics. 12: feedback@psr.gov.au plus contact section. 13A/B: Requires four clicks (Home → Publications → Corporate documents → AI statement); not in global menu. Placement is logical once in Publications, but not obvious without guidance.
Royal Australian Mint	No active AI systems; governance discussions for future readiness included. Simple but effective disclosure.	1A: Uses image processing to detect humans in security footage and Copilot/workplace productivity; goal: "improve efficiency and accuracy". 2A: Explicit: Workplace Productivity & Image Processing. 2B: States domain = Corporate & Enabling. 3A: "Mint does not use AI in a way that members of the public may directly interact with...". 3B: "Employees review all AI outputs (human in the loop)". 4B: AI Accountable Officer identified; CISO controls doc; Annual review signed by Acting CEO. 5: Cites PSPF & ISM (policies) but no legislation (e.g. Privacy Act) named. 6: Risk-based approach; no biometric ID; HITL; cyber security controls. 9B: No separate "last updated" field beyond initial date. 10: "Reviewed annually or when AI use changes".
Safe Work Australia (SWA)	Strong ethical framework and transparency for AI-assisted monitoring.	3A: "We do not propose to use AI where the public may directly interact with it." 3B: Training is required, but statement does not say every AI output is reviewed by a human. 4A: Mentions "monitoring AI effectiveness and negative impacts" but provides no cadence, metrics or method. 5: Generic: "in accordance with applicable legislation" no Acts named. 6: Says annual statement provides visibility; lacks specific mitigations (e.g. privacy impact, bias tests). 7B: No mention of Australia's eight AI Ethics Principles. 9B: No separate Last updated field. 12: Direct email businessservices@swa.gov.au provided.
Screen Australia (SA)	Minor AI engagement, mainly administrative support use.	1A: Uses AI for workplace productivity & analytics "to support our work" and improve efficiency. 2A: Explicit: "usage patterns ... workplace productivity and analytics for insights". 2B: Current domains: service delivery and corporate & enabling. 3A/B: "We do not use AI where the public may directly interact ... without a human intermediary." 4B: Chief Operating Officer named as Accountable Official with defined duties. 5: Mentions "applicable laws" but does not cite specific Acts. 8: Live page under Our Approach to AI → AI Transparency Statement. 9A/B: Only shows "last updated 24 February 2025" – no first publish date. 10: Will be reviewed at least every 12 months. 12: Direct email: ai@screenaustralia.gov.au. 13A/B: Two-click path (About us → Corporate documents → Our Approach to AI). Logical placement with other governance docs; no search needed.

Agency	Overall Observation	Criterion-level Notes
Seafarers Safety, Rehabilitation and Compensation Authority	Minimal AI involvement currently; governance readiness stressed.	1A: Statement says Seacare has no AI of its own and defers to Comcare. No purpose described. 1B: No mention of future adoption plans. 2A/B: no patterns or domains specified. 3A: Explicitly states Seacare does not use AI in any way that affects or is interacted with by the public. 3B: No description of human-in-the-loop review (because no AI outputs exist). 4A: No monitoring/evaluation process described. 4B: Names Comcare's Chief Information Office as the Accountable Official. 5: Acknowledges DTA Policy but cites no Acts (e.g. Privacy Act). 6: No risk mitigation steps outlined. 7B: Does not mention Australia's AI Ethics Principles. 8: Page live under Forms & publications → Corporate publications → AI Transparency Statement. 9A/B: Only "Page last reviewed: 11 March 2025" (no first published field). 10: No commitment to regular review. 12: Lists 1300 366 979 and Contact us link.
Services Australia (Services Australia)	Full operational AI use across service delivery systems.	1B: Only says it "may consider broader use" – no concrete roadmap. 3A: Explicit: public interacts via digital assistants. 5: Says "comply with relevant. 9A: legislation & regulations" but no Acts cited. 12: Dedicated email AI.Accountable.Official@servicesaustralia.gov.au .
Sport Integrity Australia (SIA)	Limited AI tools under testing phase; human oversight mentioned.	2A: Explicitly names "workplace productivity" pattern for Copilot. 2B: Says use sits in the "corporate and enabling" domain. 3A: Clear denial: "not authorised the use of AI in any way that members of the public may directly interact with...". 3B: Same sentence states any future public impact will have human intervention. 4B: Deputy CEO designated Accountable Official (20 Aug 2024). 5: Only generic "applicable legislation" reference; no Acts cited. 6: Mentions risk identification but lacks concrete mitigations. 7B: Statement never names Australia's eight AI Ethics Principles. 8: Live page under Corporate → Governance → AI transparency statement. 9A/B: "First published January 2025". No separate last updated stamp. 10: "Reviewed annually or when we make any significant change". 12: Provides Contact us page link, but no direct email/phone. 13A/B: Appears in the main Governance menu (two clicks from homepage). Logical placement with other governance docs; no search required.
TEQSA	Limited AI use; governance focus.	2A: Names the "workplace productivity" pattern explicitly. 3A: "Has not authorised the use of AI in service delivery" → public does not interact with TEQSA AI. 4B: Chief Information Officer named as Accountable Official; AI Steering Committee to be formed. 5: Cites DTA Policy but no specific Acts (e.g. Privacy Act 1988). 6: Mentions Steering Committee will assess risks; no concrete mitigations. Page live under About us → Reporting & accountability → AI transparency statement. 9A: "First published March 2025" shown. 9B: "Last updated 25 March 2025" visible. 10: "Reviewed annually or when significant change is made." 11: short and clear. 12: Provides Contact us link; no direct AI email → partial credit. 13A/B: AI statement in main Reporting & accountability menu (two clicks). Logical placement with other governance docs; no search needed.
Workplace Gender Equality Agency (WGEA)	Clear AI use for reporting analysis, strong governance.	3A: Clear denial: "not using AI in any way the public may directly interact with". 4A: Heading "Monitoring & accountability" but no cadence/metrics. 5: Mentions "relevant regulations & legislation" but cites none. 6: Will develop responsible AI policy; no concrete mitigations yet. 7B: "Ethical" language but doesn't list the eight AI Ethics Principles. 9A: Only "Last updated 25 Feb 2025"; no first published date. 12: Direct email wgea@wgea.gov.au provided.

Table 3. Qualitative evaluator observations and criterion-level notes for 76 of 92 evaluated agencies.

6. Agencies Without Published Statements

The following agencies were within scope of the DTA mandate at the time of data collection (May 2025) but did not have a publicly accessible AI transparency statement. No scores were assigned.

#	Agency
1	Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership (AITSL)
2	Australian National Preventive Health Agency (ANPHA)
3	Bureau of Meteorology (BoM)
4	Federal Court of Australia (FCA)
5	National Commission for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Children and Young People
6	National Competition Council (NCC)
7	Net Zero Economy Authority (NZE Authority)
8	Office of National Intelligence (ONI)